

WELDED JOINTS IN COMPOSITE STEEL BRIDGES SERVICE LIFE UNDER VARIABLE AMPLITUDE LOADING AND DIFFERENT MANUFACTURING CONDITIONS

Raphael Erlemann* and Prof. Dr.-Ing. Karsten Geißler

Technische Universität Berlin, Dept. of Conceptual and Structural Design - Steel Construction, Germany
r.erlemann@tu-berlin.de, karsten.geissler@tu-berlin.de

ABSTRACT

Box girders with steel cantilevers are often used in the design of composite steel bridges. The welded joints between the main girder and the transverse system are exposed to fatigue loading. Applicable standards for the design of the top flange joint are complex regarding the low fatigue loads being applied. One goal is the development of simplified designs with sufficient fatigue strength for these low fatigue loads. Moreover, strict tolerances for misalignments must be ensured for the cross joint at the bottom flange. It is aimed to quantify the effects of misalignments with regard to fatigue safety. For the previously mentioned joints as well as the web joint at the cantilever, manual welds are common for which the manufacturing conditions can vary in terms of welding position and environmental settings. It is therefore intended to find out whether these conditions have an influence on the fatigue strength. Besides the introduction of simplified designs and the review of manufacturing conditions, emphasis will be put on the service life estimation under variable amplitude (VA) loading. VA fatigue tests with stress spectra typical for bridge constructions were carried out to enable a review on the accuracy of service life estimation under VA loading with low peak amplitudes.

Keywords: welded joints, CA fatigue tests, VA fatigue tests, Miner hypothesis

1 INTRODUCTION AND RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Fig. 1. Illustration of a typical cross-section of a composite steel bridge with cantilevers and numbering of the notches subjected to fatigue loading at the cantilever joint for the longitudinal and transverse direction

Box girders with steel cantilevers are often used in the design of composite steel bridges with spans of 40 to 100 m. The welded joints between the main girder and the transverse system are exposed to

fatigue loading. There are various notches to consider at these joints as shown in Fig. 1, each with specific challenges depending on the load-bearing direction.

The bottom flange joint is usually close to the neutral line in the longitudinal direction, while the top flange joint is close to the neutral line in the transverse direction. This results in quasi uniaxial fatigue loading for these details with overall low stress levels and amplitudes often below the constant amplitude fatigue limit (CAFL).

Current specifications for the design of the top flange joint (Fig. 1, no. 1) are complex given the low fatigue loads being applied. High design effort with low fatigue stresses contradict each other hence it was aimed to develop simplified detail categories with sufficient fatigue safety based on large- and small-scale fatigue tests under constant amplitude (CA) loading in the high-cycle fatigue (HCF) region, that are discussed in section 2.

Besides the complex design of the top flange joint, strict limits for misalignments must be ensured for the cross joint at the bottom flange (Fig. 1, no. 2) which are difficult to ensure due to the boundary conditions of the structure. Taking into account the support of the intermediate plate, the effect of misalignments outside these currently defined limits on the fatigue strength has not been studied conclusively. Section 3 presents small-scale CA fatigue tests in the HCF region to quantify the effects of misalignments with regard to fatigue safety and in order to manage welded joints outside the allowable tolerance range.

For the previously mentioned joints as well as the web joint at the cantilever (Fig. 1, no. 3), manual welds in various positions (e.g. horizontal, rising) and environmental conditions (e.g. workshop, on site) are likely. Section 4 outlines the influence of these manufacturing conditions on the fatigue strength and their safe representation in the FAT classes of EN 1993-1-9 (1).

Alongside the introduction of simplified detail categories and the review of manufacturing conditions, section 5 puts emphasis on the service life estimation under variable amplitude (VA) loading. The service life under VA loading can be calculated by accumulating partial damages on the basis of various Miner modifications that are based on CA S-N curves in the high-cycle fatigue (HCF) region. The different Miner modifications vary in particular by the slopes of their reference S-N-curves in the very-high-cycle fatigue (VHCF) region above $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ stress cycles. The calculated service life is thus strongly dependent on the Miner modification used. However, its reliability cannot be verified without conducting VA fatigue tests. Consequently, VA fatigue tests with stress spectra typical for bridge constructions were carried out on small-scale specimen representing transverse stiffeners as can be found in the longitudinal direction of the joint under consideration (Fig. 1, no. 3). Typical for bridges are stress spectra with low peak stress amplitudes, in this case even below CAFL, and numbers of stress cycles in the range of $10^6 \leq \bar{H} \leq 10^8$. These parameters lead to long service lives, making the conducted VA fatigue tests a valuable supplement to the limited test results available and enabling a review on the accuracy of service life estimation under VA loading with low peak amplitudes.

2 TOP FLANGE JOINT – CA FATIGUE STRENGTH WITH SIMPLIFIED DESIGN

For a fatigue-resistant design of the welded joints between main and transverse system on the top flange (Fig. 1, no. 1), plate thickness tapering and a transition radius of 150 mm are currently provided, Table 2 (left), in accordance with safe sided guidelines in EN 1993-2 (2, 3) and RE-ING (4), which is a supplementary German guideline for the design and construction of civil structures published by the Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport.

The development of a simplified joint geometry with its corresponding fatigue strength as a supplement to current recommendations is a good way to facilitate execution, as the applicable standards are complex with respect to the low fatigue loads. The reinforced concrete deck of the composite bridge with its influence on the neutral line of the entire cross-section leads to low stresses at the joint.

The target of the research is the development of a simplified design with sufficient fatigue strength at significantly reduced manufacturing effort, so small-scale CA S-N tests were conducted on different simplified designs. Table 1 shows the design of the small-scale specimen and the derived experimental CA S-N curves for these test series. More detailed information on the CA S-N tests carried out on different designs can be found in (5–8).

Table 1. Specifications of differently designed small-scale specimens and corresponding experimental CA S-N curves

Illustrations and specifications of different small-scale specimens		
		Grinding of build-up weld for transition radius of 20 mm
Experimental CA S-N curves		
<p>The results from these small-scale CA S-N tests are validated and classified by large scale tests, FE parameter studies and a re-evaluation of existing test data. The derived simplified designs without plate thickness tapering, with a modified weld seam position and with a reduced transition radius show sufficiently high fatigue strengths. Simplified detail categories for the nominal stress concept according to Table 2 can be derived from the results, which are used to supplement bridge-specific regulations. These results are of particular importance for manufacturing, as this joint is often required hundreds of times per structure.</p>		
<p>Table 2. Current standard design of the cantilever top flange joint (left) and newly developed simplified designs</p>		
Top view		
Lateral view		
FAT for transverse stress amplitudes (shown in illustration)		
FAT 90	FAT 71	FAT 71
FAT for longitudinal stress amplitudes		
FAT 125	FAT 90	FAT 63

3 BOTTOM FLANGE JOINT – CA FATIGUE STRENGTH WITH MISALIGNMENT

When designing the bottom flange joint (Fig. 1, no. 2), requirements according to EN 1993-1-9 (1) put particular emphasis on ensuring a misalignment of $e \leq 15\%$ of the thickness of the intermediate plate. This proves difficult in practice, given the design conditions with an internal transverse frame and an external cantilever welded to the box girder.

It was therefore aimed to quantify the effects of misalignments exceeding the permitted tolerance on the fatigue strength. Small-scale CA S-N tests were conducted on specimen with different misalignments of $40\% \leq e \leq 80\%$. Fig. 2 shows a picture of an exemplary small-scale specimen and the derived experimental CA S-N curve for all tests. Misalignments outside the allowable tolerance according to EN 1993-1-9 (1) lead to a reduction to FAT 60 compared to FAT 71 when complying to requirements. The findings should not be used to allow misalignment in the design phase, but rather as an aid for reliable service life estimations in case the permissible tolerances are found to have been exceeded after execution. More detailed information on the CA S-N tests carried out on different designs can be found in (5–8).

Fig. 2. Picture of an exemplary small-scale specimen with misalignment (left) and corresponding experimental CA S-N curve (right)

4 WEB JOINT - CA FATIGUE STRENGTH UNDER DIFFERENT MANUFACTURING CONDITIONS

In addition to the previous aspects regarding the cantilever joint, also other aspects of quality assurance are challenging. Manual welding in different positions and environmental conditions can be assumed, e.g. manual welds in horizontal position for the bottom flange joint (Fig. 1, no. 2) or in rising position for the web joint (Fig. 1, no. 3) that are welded on site or in a workshop environment.

As these conditions are often insufficiently documented, it is not possible to differentiate between manufacturing conditions. The question therefore arises as to what extent a seam on a cross joint welded in a rising position under normal construction site conditions can be included in the normative FAT. Identical test series were produced by the same welder on a cross joint made of structural steel S355 with DHV welds for execution class EXC 3 according to (9) and classification group B according to EN ISO 5817 (10) for fatigue-stressed structures with extensive quality requirements according to EN ISO 3834 (11).

The series differ only in their manufacturing conditions (Table 3). Both series were produced using MAG welding (process 135) with ceramic weld puddle protection. Each weld consists of a root layer, an intermediate layer and a cover layer. The test series W was produced in a horizontal position (PB) under workshop conditions. Production was integrated into the daily routine of a large steel construction company with expertise in bridge construction so that no "laboratory seams" were welded. Test series B was produced in a rising position (PF) with the welder being in a tight spatial setting while squatting in summer weather without wind, i.e. normal to favourable construction site conditions. The weld parameters differ according to their manufacturing conditions.

Table 3. Summary of varying manufacturing conditions of two otherwise identical test series and corresponding experimental CA S-N curves

Test series W - workshop	Test series B - construction site
Manufacturing conditions	Manufacturing conditions
- MAG (135)	- MAG (135)
- solid wire	- cored wire
- ceramic weld puddle protection	- ceramic weld puddle protection
- PB horizontal position	- PF rising position
- favourable workshop conditions	- favourable site conditions
Welding	Welding
Experimental CA S-N curve	Experimental CA S-N curve
<p>stress amplitude $\Delta \sigma$ [MPa]</p> <p>Stress cycles N [-]</p> <p> $R = 0,1; m = 3$ $s_N = 0,0891; s_S = 0,0297$ $\Delta \sigma_c (95\%; 50\%; 5\%) = 73; 83; 95 \text{ MPa}$ </p>	

The experimental CA S-N curves show that there is a significant influence of the manufacturing conditions with their corresponding welding positions on the fatigue strength. The standard deviation in the direction of load cycles as the decisive scatter parameter of $s_N = 0,178$ in the combined evaluation of the test series (Fig. 3) is consistent with the usual assumptions from relevant literature, e.g. $s_N = 0,186$ (12). Each series has a similar distribution with only slightly differing deviations but strongly differing median fatigue strengths. A combined statistical analysis leads to the usual assumptions for scattering parameters with a broader distribution.

Fig. 3. Combined experimental CA S-N curve of the two test series with different manufacturing conditions

A large scatter in the fatigue strength of welded joints is generally known. It can be assumed that this scattering for the respective FAT class results in part from the fact that the statistical population contains different manufacturing conditions. The populations are therefore mixed when analysed together. This presumably also applies to the Eurocode database. The comparison of test series W and B shows that series W, manufactured under workshop conditions in a horizontal position, comes closest to the normative FAT 80 on the safe side. It can be seen that changed manufacturing conditions already lead to a difference of almost two FAT classes when comparing two hand-welded test series.

5 TRANSVERSE STIFFENER - VA FATIGUE STRENGTH

Besides the influences of design, manufacturing conditions and applied stress spectrum on the resulting experimental service life, the used Miner modification has a large impact on the calculated service life. The different Miner modifications for service life estimation under VA loading differ in particular by their slope in the VHCF area above $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ (Fig. 4). Miner-basic assumes no contribution to damage for amplitudes below CAFL. This results in a progression of the reference S-N curve with one bending point (Fig. 4, dashed line) and high calculated service life. In contrast, Miner-elementary is the most conservative hypothesis with a constant slope up to the abscissa (Fig. 4, solid line) and correspondingly low calculated service life. Miner-modified was developed with a second inclination and resulting service life between the two aforementioned. This second, flatter slope can be continued up to the abscissa (Fig. 4, dotted line) or up to the variable amplitude fatigue limit (VAFL at $\Delta\sigma_L / N_L$) according to EN 1993-1-9 (1), so that amplitudes below this value no longer contribute to the damage (Fig. 4, narrow dashed line).

Fig. 4. Exemplary Stress spectrum and different Miner modifications

The calculated service life is therefore strongly dependent on the Miner hypothesis used, especially for spectra typical for bridge constructions with low peak amplitudes and a large number of cycles below CAFL. The reliability of different Miner modifications can be verified experimentally. For this purpose, VA fatigue tests were carried out on specimens with transverse stiffeners using S355, which is a frequently occurring detail (Fig. 1, no. 3, longitudinal direction).

5.1 CA fatigue tests - basis for all Miner modifications

To analyse the various Miner modifications, it is important to exclude as many scattering factors as possible. As a first step, a reference S-N curve in the HCF region is necessary, which is derived from CA fatigue tests on identical specimens. Only tests with cycles to failure that were clearly within the HCF region were used for evaluation. This range was therefore narrowed down to $5 \cdot 10^4 < N < 3 \cdot 10^6$. Fig. 8 shows the resulting experimental S-N curve with an obtained FAT 97.

5.2 VA fatigue tests - experimental service life

To carry out the VA fatigue tests, load spectra typical for bridge constructions were determined, which were approximated using uniform spectra and applied as random load sequences. The uniform spectra can be mathematically described by

$$H = \bar{H}^{1-x^v} \quad (1)$$

where $x = \Delta\sigma_i/\Delta\sigma_{\max}$, H is the sum frequency, \bar{H} is the spectrum size, $\Delta\sigma_{\max}$ is the spectrum peak amplitude at $H=1$ and v defines the shape of the spectrum.

Due to the long design service life of bridge structures, the cross-section is usually dimensioned so that low peak amplitudes result for the details at risk for fatigue. For the considered specimens with an experimental FAT 97, maximum stress amplitudes of $150 \text{ MPa} \leq \Delta\sigma_{\max} \leq 250 \text{ MPa}$ were defined for the VA fatigue tests (Fig. 5). The spectrum size to be considered can be estimated on the one hand via the traffic volume. On the other hand, it should be noted that the number of load cycles can strongly be determined by individual axle passages which results in high spectrum sizes in the range of $10^6 \leq \bar{H} \leq 10^8$. Experimental experiences of the fatigue behaviour in this parameter field with high spectrum sizes \bar{H} and low peak amplitudes $\Delta\sigma_{\max}$ can hardly be found, as the corresponding VA fatigue tests are associated with long test durations due to the intended long service life of the structure.

All VA fatigue tests performed show that stress spectra with peak amplitudes of $\Delta\sigma_{\max} < 200 \text{ MPa}$ lead to runouts for the tested cycle range up to approximately $N \approx 2 \cdot 10^8$ (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Experimental VA S-N curves with linear extrapolation to lower peak amplitudes for spectrum sizes of $\bar{H} = 10^6$ (left) and $\bar{H} = 10^8$ (right)

5.3 Miner modifications - comparison of calculated and experimental service life

Fig. 6 shows the number of cycles to failure and runouts of the VA fatigue tests and the corresponding calculated service life curves based on different Miner modifications. The basis of all Miner modifications is the experimental CA S-N curve from section 5.1. The lower quantile values shown make it easier to recognize the reliability of the different Miner modifications.

For spectrum sizes of $\bar{H} = 10^6$ (Fig. 6 left), the slope of the experimental VA S-N curve is well represented by Miner-modified for the higher peak amplitudes. The runouts at low peak amplitudes are better captured by Miner-basic than by other modifications. Miner-basic thus shows the best description of the slope of the VA S-N curve for lower peak amplitudes. In addition to the appropriate slope of the VA S-N curve, the reliability of the service life prediction is particularly important. Even Miner-basic as the least conservative modification reliably captures the experimental number of cycles to failure in the upper and lower range of peak amplitudes. However, the central range with peak amplitudes of $\Delta\sigma_{\max} = 200 \text{ N/mm}^2$ is not reliable since multiple failures occurred below the 5 %-curve. Moreover, almost all experimental cycles to failure were found below the median curve for Miner-basic in the range of higher peak amplitudes. This area therefore appears to be more accurately captured by Miner-modified.

Miner-basic is thus reliable for spectra with low peak amplitudes, but only Miner-modified is on the safe side for all tested ranges. However, the service life prediction using Miner-modified is very conservative, especially for low peak amplitudes, as Miner-basic is already well on the safe side.

Fig. 6. Cycles to failure, runouts and calculated service life according to different Miner modifications for spectrum sizes of $\bar{H} = 10^6$ (left) and $\bar{H} = 10^8$ (right)

Besides the limited number of VA fatigue tests carried out for spectrum sizes of $\bar{H} = 10^8$ (Fig. 6 right), similar observations can be made. It should be noted that with a spectrum size of $\bar{H} = 10^8$, the majority of tests with peak amplitudes of $\Delta\sigma_{\max} = 200 \text{ N/mm}^2$ were stopped as runouts. Hence, regarding the slope of the experimental VA S-N curve, no robust statement can be made because of only one failure within the lower peak amplitudes. Using Miner-modified is once again on the safe side for low stress ranges.

5.4 Increased deviation of VA S-N tests with decreasing spectrum peak amplitudes

It was found that the deviation of cycles to failure increases as the peak amplitudes decrease, which means that the observed cycles to failure will lay outside the expected service lives for a linear extrapolation of the VA S-N curves to low peak amplitudes according to Fig. 5. The increased deviation can be considered reasonable, not only according to the test results (Fig. 7).

In the HCF region of CA S-N curves, the deviation in the direction of load cycles must be considered to determine the number of load cycles at which failure occurs. In the very high-cycle fatigue (VHCF) region of CA S-N curves, the deviation in the direction of the stress amplitudes must be considered in order to determine the amplitude at which failure no longer occurs. In particular, the stress spectra with low peak amplitudes contain a large number of stress amplitudes around and below CAFL (Fig. 7). The always existing scatter of the CAFL can therefore lead to considerably different experimental service lives, as the applied stress amplitudes may not only cause less damage, but no damage at all.

Fig. 7. Calculated percentage of damage by stress amplitudes above and below mean CAFL for Miner-modified for spectra with different peak amplitudes and spectrum sizes of $\bar{H} = 10^6$

5.5 Review of pre-damage on VA runouts

The specimens rated as runouts are reviewed on already induced damage by the spectra. When applying a stress spectrum with a peak amplitude of e.g. $\Delta\sigma_{\max} = 150 \text{ N/mm}^2$, the spectrum contains amplitudes below VAFL, between VAFL and CAFL, and above CAFL, so damage and service life must be calculated acc. to EN 1993-1-9 (1) with Miner-modified resulting in a limited service life. Only one part of the stress amplitudes contained in this spectrum is assumed to cause no damage, whereas the other part causes damage. The conducted VA fatigue tests carried out up to $N \approx 2 \cdot 10^8$ stress cycles have shown though, that these spectrums lead to an unlimited service life.

According to section 5.2, the spectra with the lowest peak value that still led to a failure was at $\Delta\sigma_{\max} = 200 \text{ N/mm}^2$. All conducted VA S-N tests with lower peak amplitudes were rated as runouts. These pre-loaded specimens have been used for further investigation through CA S-N tests. The distribution of the number of cycles to failure of the CA S-N tests on runout specimens (Fig. 8 left) mostly corresponds to the distribution of the number of cycles to failure of the non-preloaded specimens (Fig. 8 right). Four VA runout specimen were used for the CA S-N tests. Three of them showed cycles to failure between $118,000 \leq N \leq 147,000$, where the CA S-N test without pre-loading showed results of $N \approx 135,000$. The median value of fatigue strength remains the same for the pre-loaded and not pre-loaded specimens. This suggests that no damage was caused by the previous VA loading.

Taking the fourth test specimen into account increases the scatter and thus the deviation, which results in a lower characteristic fatigue strength. However, it should be emphasised that the increased deviation is due to an increased service life of the fourth specimen ($N \approx 223,000$). Although the characteristic fatigue strength is thus reduced, this specimen still underlines the hypothesis of a missing pre-damage.

Fig. 8. Experimental CA S-N curve for the runout specimen pre-loaded with VA spectra (left) compared to the CA S-N curve from section 5.1 (right)

The CA S-N tests conducted on the pre-loaded specimens indicate that the stress spectra with low peak amplitudes used here, which are typical for bridge construction, have not led to any pre-damage. One explanation for this could be the sequence of rare overloads (above CAFL) with long periods of low base loads, which is typical for a random load sequence of the used shape, that contains mostly stress amplitudes below CAFL, especially when having low peak amplitudes. According to (13), such a sequence can lead to slower crack growth.

Besides the justification of this observation, the question of how to handle this phenomenon is of importance. According to EN 1993-1-9 (1), section 7.1 (3), the extended fatigue strength curves with two bending points (Miner-modified) are generally to be used for spectra with amplitudes below and above CAFL. The VA S-N tests carried out with a large number of amplitudes below CAFL and low maximum values just above CAFL (approx. $1.5 \cdot \text{CAFL}$) resulted in runouts only. Based on the tests, the application of the non-extended fatigue strength curves with one bending point (Miner-basic) can therefore be recommended for corresponding spectra typical for bridge constructions. This approach would lead to a reduced and more realistic calculated damage without disrupting the basic principles of damage accumulation.

6 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Applicable standards for the design of the top flange joint are complex, therefore simplified detail categories with sufficient fatigue strength were designed. For misalignments at the bottom flange and web joint that exceed the tolerances according to EN 1993-1-9 (1) a reduction in fatigue strength from FAT 71 to FAT 60 was determined. Different manufacturing conditions for all joints

to the cantilever can be assumed, e.g. welds in horizontal or rising position welded on site or in workshop. It was found that these conditions strongly influence the resulting fatigue strength.

In addition, VA fatigue tests with up to $N \approx 2 \cdot 10^8$ stress cycles were conducted to enable a review on the accuracy of service life estimation under VA loading with low peak amplitudes which showed that stress spectra with peak amplitudes of $\Delta\sigma_{\max} < 200$ MPa did not lead to any damage or failure. It can thus be stated that Miner-modified is a very conservative approach for damage calculation when spectra typical for bridge constructions are applied.

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